

A Comparative Study of Conventional Journalism and Citizen Journalism Practices in Nigeria

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Abstract

Advancements in new forms of information and communications technologies have continued to transform content, nature, and style of writing for the media. This study examines conventional and citizen journalism practices using a comparative analysis. The objective of the study was to do a comparative analysis of conventional and citizen journalism practices and to examine the extent of usage of gate-keeping by both conventional and citizen journalists regarding fake news dissemination. The theoretical underpinnings of this study are the Technological Determinism Theory and the Technological Acceptance Model (TAM). The study adopts the comparative research design. Information was sourced from secondary sources. Based on observation and relevant information gathered from secondary sources of data, the study concludes that new information and communications technology have shaped the media ecology or environment in innumerable ways. These dynamics have introduced a new concept known as “citizen journalism” – a new form of journalism. This new form of journalism is distinct from the highly guided and rule-based conventional journalism and due to lack of gate-keeping and code of ethics is inveigled with fake news and misinformation. The study, therefore, recommends that government should develop a functional regulatory framework to regulate the social media platform to ensure sanity in the digital media landscape as the media functions not in isolation but functions within the framework of a given society.

Keywords: Media, Conventional journalism, Citizen journalism, Fake news, Misinformation, Comparative study

Introduction

The conceptualisation of the format, nature, and style employed in writing for the media has existed since the advent of the press. The press traditionally consists of the radio, television, and newspaper, classified broadly under the electronic or broadcast media and the print media forms, which includes newspaper, magazine, books, etc. Recently, the advent of digital media forms due to the rapid evolution of information and communication technology has transformed the communication and media landscape. The press is a veritable instrument in the dissemination of information, creating awareness, and ideally holding the government accountable to the people in society. The media has evolved, and certainly will continue to evolve, advance, and in contemporary times, media convergence; is a term that is used to refer to the transformation of traditional media forms into new media forms and the addition of new functions to all the experiences of traditional media. This gave rise to a new brand of journalism practice popularly known as citizen journalism.

Traditional media writing is guided by a defined gate-keeping process aimed at standardisation and quality control. Gate-keeping is at the heart of conventional journalism practice and it focuses on generating objective, ethical, and relatively error-free content for dissemination to the audience. Accordingly, Guanah et al. (2019):

Before the advent of the new media, the professional journalist through gate-keeping ensured that only credible items that could enable democratic society and make the people better citizens are released as news. Before the news gets to the public sphere, it would have been subjected to the professional view of the gate-keepers starting with the reporter who gathered the news (p. 426).

Gate-keeping in journalism constitutes a fundamental factor in the news production process. it involves the consideration of certain related but intervening factors as parameters for allowing or rejecting possible editorial contents of the media. Lending credence to the above, Ihejirika et al. (2014) assert that:

from the different sub-editors, the story moves over to the editor... the editor or the editorial board makes the final decision on what to publish or broadcast. It keeps in mind the intention of the proprietor, the financial needs of the media organisation of (sic) the legal implication of the write-up (p. 10).

This rigorous and extended information filtration process known as gate-keeping describes a refining process for media content, aimed at producing, and disseminating credible news stories devoid of misinformation, disinformation, indecent publications, and litigations. These features characterised the conventional journalism practice. Conventional journalism practice is regulated by media law, and press professional ethics. (Hassan, 2014, p. 107) points out that “gate-keeping involves setting certain standards and limitations that serve as guidelines for both content development and delivery of a mass communication message”. Expatiating on this, Rodman (2012) stated:

producers of mass media messages are often called gate-keepers because they determine which messages will be delivered to media consumers, how those messages will be constructed, and when they will be delivered. Sponsors, editors, producers, reporters, and executives all have the power to influence traditional mass media messages. These messages are shaped by a wide range of economic, ethical, and legal considerations (p. 8).

Information dissemination is one key role played by the mass media, particularly conventional journalism with the potential to contribute to or forestall human and societal progress. Conventional journalism also known as traditional journalism conveys messages to the public through traditional platforms such as newspapers, television, and radio, it is however, known to have more informative and detailed content than its digital media rivals; it is also known for its formality and structure.

The notion or concept of citizen journalism is a difficult term to define but the following definition will suffice for this study, because of the technical, inclusive, functional, and broad encapsulation of its key elements:

citizen journalism or participatory journalism is the act of everyday citizens – without professional journalism training or experience- playing an active role in collecting, reporting and analysing the news. Through citizen journalism, non-journalists can use modern technology and the global distribution of the internet to create news stories (Rodman, 2012, p. 312).

The extrapolation of the above definition brings to the fore that citizen journalists are non-professionals, and consequently lacks adequate knowledge of the ethics of the journalism profession. Further, is the fact that since they (citizen journalists) make use of information and communication technology informally to create and disseminate news, it's obvious that gate-keeping is absent or better still limited. Accordingly, Ojiaku and Ekwunife (2020b, p. 627-628) inform that “the practice of citizen journalism is not professional journalism; hence, every Tom, Dick, and Harry gets involved with little or no training; straining the gate-keeping process of professional journalism”.

Mass media as a form of journalism is driven by new technologies, audience segmentation needs, and new social demands. The advent of new technology comes with significant and dynamic socio-economic, hardware, and professional modifications: in fact, scholars observed that new professional fields have emerged within existing professions, and journalism is no exception. However, every new technology comes with a format, nature, and style of writing, as well as the means of using them. Advancements in information and communication technology continue to develop and are subject to change at all times. Nevertheless, any new research into a comparative analysis of conventional and citizen journalism practice can still exploit the opportunity to fill a gap within the existing literature.

Statement of the problem

The conceptualisation of contemporary media writing bifurcates into two perspectives: conventional and citizen journalism practices. This classification typology is based on a holistic assessment of the parameters and established principles employed in either conventional, traditional or citizen journalism. Conventional journalism is characterised by gate-keeping and strict adherence to codes of professional ethics in content generation and dissemination of the different genres of mass media. These rigid control processes are aimed at improving the news content to meet standards, as well as to avoid issues of litigation arising from libel or slander, seditious publications, indecent/ obscene publications, and misinformation.

While the citizen journalism practice is a kind of gathering information and dissemination of news by citizens using information and communication devices such as phablets, tablets, laptops, etc. Such news is mostly unprocessed and raw as it is devoid of any form of formal gatekeeping process. This scenario, in many instances, has led to widespread misinformation, lies, indecent publication, and the publication of obscene materials. (Self 1996, p. 241 cited in Udoudo & Osere, 2017, p.6) observed that “credibility is the believability, trust, perceived reliability and sources and combinations of other concepts”

This situation is worrisome, particularly in a profession that is constitutionally recognised and referred to as the Fourth Estate of the Realm with prized credibility and as a bastion of reliability by the audience. The emphasis or focus of this study, therefore, is to explore the canons of journalistic ethics as a basis of the epistemological foundation for a comparative analysis of the conventional and citizen journalism practice in contemporary media writing. This is necessary since effective journalism practice requires sound knowledge of journalistic ethics without which practitioners are likely to function or go about their professional practice in a manner that offends the professional code of ethics.

Study objectives

The following objectives guided this study:

1. To do a comparative analysis of the conventional and citizen journalism practice in Nigeria.
2. To examine the extent of usage of gate-keeping by both conventional and citizen journalists concerning fake news dissemination.

Methodology

This study adopts the comparative research design. It is mainly qualitative which draws data through observation, relevant books, journals, and related materials from conference articles. Comparative research essentially compares two groups, events, or phenomena intending to draw a conclusion about them. The study attempts to identify and analyse similarities and differences between conventional and citizen journalism practices. Comparative studies are useful in increasing the understanding between conventional and citizen journalism and could create a foundation for disseminating credible news stories. These differences and similarities are identified qualitatively using secondary data.

Theoretical framework

Theories are important and useful to any empirical study because they provide the latitude for analysis aimed at predicting phenomena for any research. To provide a sound base for this study, two related communication theories are adopted, namely, Technological Determinism Theory and the Technological Acceptance Model.

Technological Determinism Theory

There is disagreement among scholars on who developed or propounded the technological determinism theory. While the majority support the proposition that it was Marshal McLuhan who postulated the technological determinism theory in 1962, others argue that the term “technological determinism” was believed to have been coined by an American sociologist and economist Thorstein Veblen (1857 – 1929).

Technological determinism theory posits that the advent of new technology has a dynamic and fundamental impact on not just the individual but also society. As it relates to communication and media studies, the introduction of new information and communications technology shapes the nature, pattern, and structure of interaction among individuals, as well as institutional structures that use symbolic content to disseminate information to the audience members. Accordingly, Ude-Akpeh et al. (2020) explicitly state that “media technology shapes how we, as individuals in a society think, feel, act, and how society operates, as we move from one technology age to another” (p. 223). Similarly, Croteau and Hoynes (2005) define technological determinism as an approach that identifies technology, or technological advances, as the central causal element in processes of social change.

Rodman (2012) explains that “the introduction of every new technology changes society, sometimes in unexpected ways” (p. 60). Burton (2010, p. 201) also asserts that “it represents an argument that technology of itself shapes society and can be a course of social change”. According to Baran and Davies (2006, p. 303), “a technological determinist is a person who believes that all societal, political, economic and cultural changes are inevitably based on the development and diffusion of technology”. Pavlik and McIntosh (2013) also affirm that “technology causes certain human behaviours” (p. 454). As it relates to this study, since the theory underpins that technology change determines the use and adaptations, epistemological dimensions necessitate an investigation into contemporary writing for the media. Here lies the relevance of this theory to the study.

Technological Acceptance Model (TAM)

The Technological Acceptance Model (TAM) was developed by Fred Davies in 1989. (Silva & Dias, 2007, p. 77) inform that “The Technology Acceptance Model, most known as technology acceptance model (TAM), was proposed by Davis (1989), being an adaptation of the model Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA)”. Davis proposed that an individual's information systems acceptance is determined by two major variables: Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU). Perceived Usefulness (PU) refers to the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would enhance his or her job performance, while Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) is the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would be free from effort. Accordingly, Jumbo et al. (2020, p. 21) alluding to the above proposition, posit that “the principle of the model is that when a new information system (such as digital media), is introduced, the possibility that the target users will adopt it; is hinged on two factors: the usefulness and the perceived ease of application. The first factor is based on how this technology will be useful to the user, while the second factor centres on the assumption that the use of the system would be simple and free from constraints. The core tenet of the technology acceptance model holds that potential or prospective users of a new technology system come to accept and use it; here lies the relevance of this theory. However, “TAM is comprised of four constructs: perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, attitudes, and actual behaviours” (Deslonde & Becerra, 2018, p. 369).

Conceptual review

A contemporary approach to writing for the mass media is an attempt to examine issues that relate to the nature, format, technological application, and ethical considerations of journalism practice, particularly with the coalesce of media forms or media convergence leading to the advent of the digital media platform. Writing for the media is a skilful art and a guided process. The journalists in course of discharging their duties constantly experience a wide range of events and activities to

cover. The journalists, therefore, are responsible to society, not only to present accounts of such events but to present them in contexts that make meaning. It behoves journalists to give careful consideration to the formats, techniques, structures, and styles that go with the packaging of stories for the mass media.

Conventional/traditional journalism

Conventional/Traditional journalism is a form of journalism that is the practice of gathering and disseminating news stories through a protracted gate-keeping process mainly in the print or broadcast media. It allows journalists to gather and report news stories more accurately and comprehensively than citizen journalism practice. Talking about the relevance of conventional or traditional media, Pavlik and McIntosh (2013) inform that “digital technology and the internet will continue to transform journalism, but professional, mainstream journalism today is still largely practiced as it has been” (p. 289). The extrapolation is that journalism practice has a purpose and procedure for reporting. Thinking along this line of thought, Hasan (2014, p. 178) posits that “the central purpose of journalism is to provide citizens with accurate and reliable information they need to function in a free society”.

Citizen journalism

Citizen journalism is the practice of gathering and disseminating information by individuals who are not trained journalists by taking advantage of the potential of digital technology. In corroborating the above proposition, Ekwunife et al. (2020b) posit that “citizen journalism (CJ) refers to the involvement of ordinary citizens in news gathering and dissemination” (Kolodzy, 2011, p. 110), as cited in Ojiaku and Ekwunife (2020) inform that “citizen journalism refers to a citizen playing an active role in the process of collecting, reporting, analysing and disseminating news and information”. Onyinye and Onyebi (2018) contend that “when a common man in his capacity as a citizen of a nation takes up the initiative to report things or expresses his views about what happens around him, then the practice is popularly termed citizen journalism or participatory journalism” (p. 322).

There is no gain in saying that, citizen journalists have transformed the media landscape, particularly concerning news gathering, processing, and dissemination. Citizens are now active participants in the creation and production of news giving rise to what is today known as the PROSUMER phenomenon in media and communication studies. It simply means the audience is producers as well as consumers of news. Likewise, Pavlik and McIntosh (2011, p. 300) argue that “the internet and especially social-media tools have allowed the rapid growth of what is called citizen journalism. Although it takes many forms, and is still being defined”.

Interestingly, since the advent of digital media platforms, there exists a noticeable change in paradigm in the communications landscape from a passive audience receiver phenomenon to user-generated content (UGC). The overriding philosophy behind citizen journalism is to create citizens’ access to the media and for the citizens to play an active role in the processes of collecting, reporting, analysing, and disseminating news or information. This has transformed the citizens from content consumers to content producers, which McQuail describes as the PROSUMER phenomenon.

This unfettered access of citizens to the internet and the practice of the PROSUMER concept have led to the introduction and spread of fake news, misinformation as well as dissemination of obscene and indecent content in cyberspace. Digital media platforms have become tools of abuse by citizen journalists; who probably knew nothing about the codes and ethical standards of journalism practice. Accordingly, Oberiri (2016, p. 443) observed that citizen journalism “has increased the craze of unethical practices (where anyone can just write and disseminate information on the web without editing) thereby threatening the integrity and dignity of the journalism profession”. This line of thought was also expressed by Ojiaku and Ekwunife (2020, p. 628) where they argue that “since CJ is carried out by ordinary citizens who are not trained to do

the job, the credibility of the reportage remains problematic...citizen journalism is devoid of gate-keeping which makes professional journalism distinct”.

Imperative of gate-keeping in journalism practice

Gate-keeping in news gathering is the process of filtering or sifting information for dissemination through the mass media. Accordingly, Ihejirika et al. (2014, p. 9) posit that “media contents pass through many gates before they get to the public”. It is a refining process in journalism to provide credible information to the public, gate-keeping is, therefore, a necessary factor in any form of journalism practice.

Guanah et al. (2019, p. 426) inform that “when information is given in relation to an occurrence, such information is not counted newsworthy until it has been made to pass through the necessary gates that will qualify it as news”. Gate-keeping is a necessary and fundamental factor in journalism, any good piece of journalistic writing in the public domain is the product of gate-keeping – from the reporter to sub-editor to news editor to the editor-in-chief.

Conceptual clarification of fake news and misinformation

Conventional journalism by its nature of content generation is said to be less prone to issues of journalistic ethics such as fake news, but citizen journalism is susceptible to issues of journalistic ethics such as fake news, misinformation, and disinformation. This, however, is attributed to the nature and potential of social media platforms via technology. The concept and meaning of fake news itself is a threat and a detriment to socio-economic cum political well-being of a nation, as well as a threat to the harmonious relationship that exists in any nation.

Fake news refers to news stories or news articles intentionally or accidentally created and disseminated through the media. They are designed to manipulate the target audience's perception of real facts, statements, or occurrences. It is information knowingly presented by the promoter as news that is verifiably untrue based on demonstrable facts. There exists an overlap between fake news, misinformation, and disinformation. Misinformation is false or misleading information, while disinformation refers to false information deliberately and purposely spread to mislead the target audience. Misinformation is generally used to refer to false information disseminated regardless of whether the intent is to mislead or not. It also implies information is generated and spread without a deliberate intent to cause harm.

Nunez (2018, p. 223) opines that “fake news has assumed a disturbing element and its damaging implications cut across every walk of life, ranging from politics, religion, business, social life, and national security”. In discussing the type of media that is guilty of fake news, Dahiru and Muhammed (2021) stated that “the advent of digital technologies escalated the dangers of misinformation, disinformation and propaganda otherwise known as fake news” (p. 244). This implies that social media are more prone to disseminating fake news. Scholars have argued that there is a major challenge in managing social media in Nigeria. Accordingly, Beckley (2018) posits that “one major challenge in managing social media in Nigeria is the lack of regulatory law in the Nigerian Communications Act (NCA).

Regulatory agencies and their functions

It is pertinent at this juncture to examine the specific functions of the various regulatory agencies to have a good grasp of the contradistinction between conventional journalism practice and citizen journalism practice.

Nigeria Communications Commission (NCC)

The Powers of the Nigerian Communications Commission are derived from Section 3 of the Nigerian Communications Acts (NCA) of 2003. The following are the functions performed by the NCC:

1. Giving written directions to licensees.
2. Consulting with consumers, and commercial and industrial organisations.
3. Delegating its functions to a committee constituted by it.
4. Summoning persons to appear before the commission.

5. Entering into contracts with any company, firm, or persons.
6. Establishing and maintaining subsidiaries to enable the discharge of its functions.
7. With Issuance of licenses and imposition of terms and conditions on licenses.
8. Variation or revocation of a condition of license.
9. Consulting with affected licensees before bringing into force an obligation that may be onerous on the licensee.
10. Approving guidelines for keeping accounts and cost allocation formulas of licensees.
11. Inspection of licensees' books of accounts.
12. Granting or revoking of permits for connection of customer equipment.
13. Determination of principles to guide interconnection arrangements between operators.
14. Determination of services and new undertakings eligible for licensing from time to time.

Nigerian Press Council

The Nigerian Press Council is one of the regulatory agencies or bodies responsible for the unbiased dissemination of information; maintaining a high level of professionalism, and ensuring ethical standards are complied with. The Nigerian Press Council focuses more on the print media of the mass media classification typologies. Some of its functions amongst others are:

1. Training of journalists.
2. Ensure inclusive and collaborative regulatory agency regulation aimed at professionalism.
3. Research on standards, etc.

Advertising Practitioners Council of Nigeria (APCON)

The following are the functions performed by the Advertising Practitioners Council of Nigeria:

1. Acts as a watchdog for consumers
2. Regulates and promotes ethical advertising
3. Acts as the conscience of society
4. Admits advertising practitioners to the council
5. Organises training workshops/seminars for the acquisition of advertising skills and requisite knowledge among practitioners.

National Broadcasting Commission (NBC)

National Broadcasting Commission performs the under listed functions:

1. Regulates all terrestrial radio, and television broadcasting services.
2. Issues licenses to cable and direct-to-home (DTH) services.
3. Sets standards regarding the content and quality of materials broadcast throughout Nigeria.

However, all the regulatory agencies are created to ensure that contents generated by the media that go out to the public do not offend public sensibilities but promote sanity and national unity.

The only regulatory framework for the social media platform is the National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA).

National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA)

This Agency develop a code of practice for interactive computer service platforms, internet intermediaries, and conditions for operating in Nigeria which aimed at standardisation, coordination, and development of regulatory frameworks for all information technology (IT) practices in Nigeria. Its functions include:

1. To develop guidelines for electronic governance
2. To develop guidelines for the networking of public and private sector establishment
3. To maintain orderliness in the online ecosystem.

This code of practice was said to have been developed in collaboration with the Nigeria Communications Commission (NCC) and National Broadcasting Commission (NBC). The code is expected to restore sanity in Nigeria's internet space and possibly regulate practices of digital media platforms.

How much have the regulatory bodies influenced the output of the various media?

In Nigeria, the media regulatory agencies have in some instances influenced the output of the various media, particularly, the Broadcasting Organisation of Nigeria (BON). Instances abound where BON has influenced the output of the African Independent Television (AIT) by closing down the station for non-adherence to the professional code of ethics. Several radio stations all over the states in Nigeria have been closed down also for violation of the professional code of ethics. For instance, the Agency Report in Premium Times of July 28, 2018, titled “Nigerian government clamps down on Ray Power’s ‘political platform’; imposes fine”. The report reads in part “The National Broadcasting Commission (NBC), has fined DAAR Communications (owner of AIT/Raypower) N500,000 for persistent violation of the provisions of the Nigeria Broadcasting Code. NBC’s Head of Public Affair, Maimuna Jimada, via a statement issued on Saturday in Abuja, said comments made on Raypower’s programme “Political Platform” was against the broadcasting code. Mrs. Jimada stated that the organisation was sanctioned due to “provocative, inflammatory and divisive comments” by anchors of the political platform. She said the Commission on May 2, 2017, Aug. 15, 2017, and February 2018, held meetings with staff of DAAR Communications to caution them on the unprofessional manner of anchors of the programme. She stated that the Commission had charged the team handling the programme to be fair, and balanced in their reportage. According to her, during the Feb. 7 meeting, the Commission stressed the need to comply with the broadcasting code to avoid sanctions.

Also on October 16th, 2022, the Zamfara State Security Council approved and ordered the closure of some media outlets in the state for breaking the laws of journalism. The affected media houses were Radio Nigeria, Pride FM Gusau, NTA Gusau, Gamji Television, Vision FM, and Al Umma TV. These are instances among others that regulatory agencies have attempted to influence the output or the content of various media. Further, the Sun newspaper edition of 23, November 2022 reported a roundtable organised by Daria Media and MacArthur foundation aimed at obtaining media stakeholders' buy-in of the Ombudsman framework and the revised Code of Ethics of Journalists in Nigeria. The roundtable was organized against the backdrop of attacks on press freedom and media independence including through legislation by the government following the wrong perception that the media is unwilling to regulate itself; the poor state of compliance with ethical and professional standards by some journalists and editors; and the pollution of the information sphere by misinformation and disinformation.

Comparative analysis of conventional/traditional versus citizen journalism practice

Table 1: Comparative analysis table

Parameters of comparison	Conventional journalism	Citizen journalism
Definition	Conventional journalism refers to ethically practiced journalism that is guided by media law	citizen journalism refers to citizens' active involvement in news dissemination, and it comes with a few more intricacies
Conveyed through	Through the mediums of radio, television, news magazines, newspapers, and their online offshoots.	Through technology platforms such as blogs, podcasts, social media, and YouTube
Ethical issues	Professional code of ethics guiding the conduct of practitioners	Without a professional code of conduct
Credibility	High level of credibility in terms of practitioners and media institutions	Lacks credibility, as its operations are enmeshed in pseudonym
Professional training	They are qualified, trained, and vetted journalists	Most of them are not trained professionals
Gatekeeping	It follows a rigid gate-keeping process for the refinement of news stories	There is no gate-keeping process for citizen journalism practice, most practitioners act independently
Reporting strategy	Objectivity and balance in reporting	They immerse themselves in the story, reporting firsthand, and immediately broadcast the uncensored footage online
Frequency of reporting	The frequency of reporting could be daily, weekly, or monthly depending on the medium	Of instant reporting as the news breaks or unfolds. There is no time orientation.
Concern for public interest	It must be of interest to the public	Without regard to the public interest
Expertise	Practitioners possessed the expertise and have good professional credentials	Most practitioners lack expertise and have no professional credentials
Regulation	Regulated using institutionalised regulatory	No clear functional regulation

	agencies/bodies	
Regulatory agencies	Nigerian Communications Council (NCC), National Broadcasting Commission (NBC). Nigerian Press Council, Advertising Practitioners Council of Nigeria (APCON).Nigerian Guild of Editors (NGE), and Nigerian Union Of Journalists(NUJ), Among others.	National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA),

*This table demonstrates the parameters of comparison between conventional and citizen journalism practices in Nigeria.

Discussions

In Nigeria, there are different and numerous regulatory bodies of the traditional media. However, the Sun Newspaper of 23rd November 2022 in its Front Page headline disclosed a new regulatory framework titled, “Media Adopts New Co-Regulation Framework, Code of Ethics”. The paper reported that “the Nigerian media has adopted the new co-regulation and code of ethics to address ethical and professional concerns in the industry”. The proliferation of regulatory agencies, it is argued, has brought about duplication and overlapping functions. While the citizen journalism practice is yet to have a well-established and functional regulatory platform though nascent, it has at the moment “National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA). In alluding to the above statement, UNESCO (2018, p. 8) informs that:

the spread of disinformation and misinformation is made possible largely through social networks and social messaging, which begs the question of the extent of regulation and self-regulation of companies providing these services. In their character as intermediary platforms, rather than content creators, these businesses have to date generally been subject to only light-touch regulation (except in the area of copyright).

Similarly, Zeenat O. Sambo, Premium Times, June 21, 2022, in her article titled “of regulation and Nigeria’s new social media code of practice” posits that “before this development, various laws and guidelines on information and communications technology(ICT) have been in place but none, specifically, governs the social media platforms and the users”

Comparatively, conventional journalism practice is said to be more credible because practitioners are mostly professionally trained or have gained expertise through practice. While citizen journalists at best can be described as a dilettante. They are not professionally trained but leverage only the potential of social media technology. On the aspect of gate-keeping, conventional journalism follows a rigid gate-keeping process for the refinement of news stories. While there is no gate-keeping process for citizen journalism practice, most practitioners act independently and are inexperienced.

The regulatory agencies for conventional journalism are the Nigerian Communications Council (NCC), National Broadcasting Commission (NBC). Nigerian Press Council, Advertising Practitioners Council of Nigeria (APCON).Nigerian Guild of Editors (NGE), and Nigerian Union Of Journalists (NUJ), Among others. However, citizen journalism practice as a new form of journalism has few regulatory frameworks, as well as policies. As indicated in the above table, it is only the National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) that tends to regulate the citizen journalism practice.

Conclusion

At the end of an extensive examination of contemporary writing for the media using a comparative analysis of the conventional and citizen journalism practice, the study concludes that new information and communications technology shapes the media ecology or environment in innumerable ways. This is evident in the present media convergence where new forms of journalism have emerged. One such journalism is citizen journalism. This form of journalism is distinct from conventional journalism which the nature and process of writing are guided and immersed in a

series of professional codes of ethics aimed at refining the news story. However, the citizen journalism practice is devoid of gate-keeping and ethical codes of practice, and to that extent is mostly frosted with fake news and misinformation leading to credibility problems and issues of pseudonyms.

Recommendations

1. Government should develop a functional regulatory framework to regulate the social media platform to ensure sanity in the digital media landscape as the media functions within the framework of a given society.
2. The study also recommends citizen journalists adoption of the new co-regulation, and code of ethics designed to address ethical and professional concerns in the industry reached by media chiefs and operators at the roundtable organised on Monday, November 14th, 2022 by the Newspaper Proprietors Association of Nigeria (NPAN) in conjunction with the Nigerian Guild of Editors (NGE), Nigeria Union of Journalists (NUJ), Broadcasting Organisation of Nigeria (BON), and the Guild of Corporate Online Publishers(GOCOP).

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